

Chemical Aspects of Carbon Assimilation.*

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I thank you most heartily for the honour you have done me by electing me your President. When just twelve years ago the leading chemists and some distinguished physicists of our country brought to me at Madras as the President of the Chemical Section of the Indian Science Congress, an application requesting me to take steps for the formation of an Indian Chemical Society and a strong committee with the late Dr. E. R. Watson as chairman was appointed, I was doubtful whether the country would realise the importance of the steps that we were taking in founding an Indian Chemical Society. It is a matter of extreme satisfaction to all of us that in the short period of twelve years, the Indian Chemical Society is a well organised, learned institution with a fairly large membership and an important Journal, the success of which goes to the friendly co-operation of Indian Chemists of all sections and to the generosity of the Calcutta University for printing it free of cost. The most pressing need of the Society seems to be the increase in the number of Fellows and the collection of donations from our Fellows as well as from industrial magnates and others concerned with the progress of the country, for increasing the permanent fund of the Society.

There is one more topic concerning our Society on which I venture to say a few words. Sometimes it has been urged that there is unnecessary delay in the publication of papers, which under our rules have to be carefully scrutinised by at least two competent authorities on the subject matter of the paper. If I may state my own experience, frequently papers written by me have been criticised and improvements suggested by referees, and I have generally found that the papers have improved by the alterations put forward. I beg of authors of papers to put up with the criticisms of the referees and alter their presentation according to the suggestions made by the

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referees, and I am sure of the majority of cases, the papers will improve in presentation.

Following the practice of my predecessors, I shall discuss from the chemical view-point one of the most fundamental problems of science in which chemists, botanists, physiologists, and agriculturists have taken a considerable interest and a problem on which our life on this earth depends. I mean the production of food and fuel from carbonic acid. The importance of this problem has long been realised.

Introduction.

The following conversation is said to have passed between Stephenson, the famous discoverer and engineer and Buckland, the celebrated geologist when they watched a railway train vanish rapidly in the distance.

“ Well, Buckland,” said Stephenson as he looked at the famous geologist, “ what is it that drives the yonder train along? ”

“ Well,” answered the geologist, “ I should think that it is one of your great engines.”

“ Yes, but what moves the engine? ”

“ Why, one of your Newcastle engineers”.

“ No, sunlight.”

“ How can that be ?” asked the geologist.

“ I assure you it is nothing else ” replied the engineer.

“ It is light that has been stored in the earth for many thousands of years ; the light absorbed by the plant during its growth is essential for the condensation of carbon, and this light which has been hidden in the coal for so many years, is now unearthed and being set free as in this engine, serves human beings.”

The organic compounds synthesised by the plants are partly used up by them for their own food, but the greater part of these energy-rich organic substances, which are products of their labour are stored in their own bodies. A small part of this stored up materials is required for and used up as seeds and thus succeeding generations of plant life continue on the earth's surface. The majority of the energy-producing compounds manufactured by plant is, however, used by animals for their existence.

It appears, therefore, that in plants, in presence of sunlight the preparation of food materials and the consumption of a portion of the manufactured food can go on simultaneously. Animals, however,

consume the food manufactured by the plants and cannot produce their own nutrients in their body like the plants. Hence from this point of view, plant machinery is superior to that of the animal.

From times immemorial men came to the conclusion that all energy must ultimately come to us from the sun and therefore sun was worshipped as the All Father, the Giver of all good. The sun is the source of all our wealth, power and life. The radiation from the sun amounts to more than 3×10^{33} calories per year. Of this amount the earth only receives 133×10^{22} calories.

It is estimated that the plants convert per year sixty billion kilograms of carbon dioxide to useful organic substances. It has been calculated that only 1/10,000 part of the total solar energy received on the surface of the earth is utilised in the formation of useful organic substances.

In this connection the following observations of L. J. Henderson are of interest :—“ Two chemical individuals stand alone in importance for the great biological cycle upon earth. The one is water, the other carbon dioxide. These two simple substances are the common sources of every one of the complicated substances which are produced by living beings and they are the common end-products of the wearing away of all the constituents of the protoplasm and of the destruction of those materials which yield energy to the body”.

It is clear, therefore, that life on the earth rests on the energy obtained from the sun through the phenomenon of photosynthesis going on in plants. Man depends entirely on this solar energy, which is made available to him by agricultural pursuits.

In photosynthesis, nature has evolved a method of storing the energy of the sun and it is the only photochemical change known in which energy is stored up for the use of mankind.

Efficiency of Carbon Assimilation not High.

Unfortunately the efficiency of this most important chemical change is not of a high order. Pütter (1914) found that about 3% of the solar energy is utilised by various crops. Oats use 3.31%, potatoes 3.02%, beets 2.12%, wheat 3.26%, and barely from 2.6 to 3.68%. According to Miller (1928), only 2.2% of the total radiation falling on an acre of land in Kansas (U. S. A.) under field conditions is utilised by corn for carbohydrate formation.

History.

Priestley (1773) and Scheele, who are discoverers of oxygen gas, also independently and simultaneously studied the problem of carbon assimilation, but their conclusions were diametrically opposite. While Priestley's plants improved the air rendered unfit by the animals, Scheele's plants produced carbon dioxide, because neither Priestley nor Scheele realised the importance of light in these experiments. Ingen-Housz (1779-1796) discovered the importance of light in this reaction and seems to have realised the cosmical function of green plants aided by sunlight and the relation between plant and animal nutrition. Senebier (1783-1800) appears to be the first to show that evolution of oxygen by plants in sunlight is accompanied by the absorption of CO_2 and not that of air. He also observed that it was not the solar heat but light, which causes the liberation of CO_2 in plants. Moreover, he was also the first to show that the red part of the solar spectrum was most active in the decomposition of carbonic acid. De Saussure (1804), who was highly influenced by Lavoisier's quantitative studies, introduced quantitative observations in this subject and came to the conclusion from rather crude experiments that the volume of oxygen evolved by plants is the same as that of carbon dioxide absorbed. He observed that the plants gain in weight by the intake of carbonic acid gas. He definitely established that carbon dioxide was absolutely necessary for the growth of plants from experiments carried on with plants kept in a confined space from which carbon dioxide was removed by potassium hydroxide. He showed that the plants died under these conditions, and also observed that oxygen is necessary for plant life and in an atmosphere of nitrogen and carbon dioxide plants cannot live. The importance of water in photosynthesis was also recognised by de Saussure. He appears to have introduced the idea of photosynthetic and respiratory quotients. Hence he extended our knowledge on this subject considerably, chiefly as a result of his quantitative methods.

Although Priestley, Ingen-Housz, Senebier and de Saussure believed that the green parts of the plant were active in the absorption of carbon dioxide and liberation of oxygen, Dutrochet in 1867 established the fact that the presence of chlorophyll in the green parts of the plants was responsible for the assimilation of carbon dioxide. In numerous publications Liebig (1840) was the first to

emphasise that carbon dioxide present in the air formed the only source of carbon for the plant life. It will, however, be shown later on that plants absorb carbon dioxide from the soil as well as from the atmosphere. Although the researches of von Mohl (1851) and Unger (1855) were important in showing that carbohydrates are the first substances to be produced in photosynthesis, Sachs (1862) was the pioneer to show that starch was the first visible product formed by the plant leaf from carbon dioxide absorption. This great botanist was also the first to make the important observation that when leaves rich in starch are placed in the dark, they lose starch. It appears again when the starch-free leaves receive light. Later on, Meyer (1885) showed that there is a group of plants *e. g.*, *Asclepias cornuti* and many *Monocotyledons*, most *Compositæ*, *Umbelliferae*, etc., which do not form starch but sugars in photosynthesis. Hence starch need not always be the first visible product of photosynthesis as advocated by Sachs.

The crude experiments of de Saussure were considerably improved by the great agricultural chemist Bossingault (1864), but his conclusions were the same as that of de Saussure regarding the ratio of the volume of carbon dioxide absorbed and oxygen evolved. The chemical change involved in carbon assimilation is usually represented by the following equation:

Actual Velocities of Carbon Assimilation.

Blackman and Miss Matthaei (1905) obtained the following results with *Helianthus tuberosus*. In brilliant August sunshine at Cambridge, at a temperature varying from 29.3° to 31° in an atmosphere containing 6.3% carbon dioxide, the assimilation was 0.022 g. of CO₂ for 50 sq. cm. of leaf surface and 5.8 g. of CO₂ per sq. m. of the leaf surface per hour. Willstätter and Stoll (1918) reported that 8 g. of CO₂ per sq. m. of the leaf surface with *Helianthus annuus* and 6.3 g. for the same surface and temperature with *Cucurbita pepo* are absorbed. These results of Willstätter and Stoll are the highest values of carbon assimilation obtained so far under artificial conditions. Miller (1917) has stated that the average velocity of carbon assimilation in air during a period of ten hours for pumpkin, cow peas and soy beans corresponds to 1.8, 0.85 and 0.8 mg. carbohydrate per hour per sq. dcm. of the leaf surface. The velocity for *pumpkin* as observed by Miller

is practically the same as that obtained by Sachs (1884) for *Helianthus annuus*. Working with *Hydrilla*, Sir J. C. Bose obtained the value 28 mg. per sq. dcm. of leaf surface per hour; this is the maximum rate observed by Sir J. C. Bose. These velocities of carbon assimilation are much less than those obtained by Blackman and Matthaei and Willstätter and Stoll and others under artificial conditions using much larger concentrations of carbon dioxide.

It is of interest to note that the velocity of photosynthesis in Philippine Islands with leaves of sugar cane, cocoanut, etc., is reported by McLean (1920) to be small and the maximum absorption of carbon dioxide by sugar cane leaves corresponds to 0.35 mg. of carbohydrate per sq. dcm. per hour under natural conditions. It appears likely that the high temperature in the Philippine Islands causes a marked acceleration of respiration and hence the velocity of photosynthesis appears to be small. It seems, therefore, that in tropical countries photosynthesis need not be high even when the light intensity is large, because of the increase of respiration, which opposes photosynthesis.

Influence of the Concentration of Carbon Dioxide on Carbon Assimilation and some Practical Applications.

Warburg (1922), from careful experiments on the unicellular alga, *Chlorella*, kept at 25°, and exposed to radiations from a metal filament lamp giving out light of intensity greater than that of direct sunlight, has concluded that at low concentrations of carbon dioxide, the velocity of photosynthesis is almost directly proportional to the carbon dioxide content (concentration of CO₂ from 1/120 to 10 times the normal amounts present in air). When the concentration of CO₂ is greater than 2×10^{-6} mol. per litre, increase in the concentration of CO₂ causes a smaller increase in the velocity of photosynthesis. In the final stages of the concentration, the velocity of photosynthesis seems to be independent of CO₂ concentration.

Harder (1921) has studied this problem with aquatic plants much more systematically and has come to the conclusion that the higher the light intensity the greater will be the increasing effect of an enhancement of carbon dioxide concentration. Lundegårdh's experiments (1924) with land plants show that when the light intensity is $\frac{1}{40}$ th of that of sunlight, an increase in photosynthetic

velocity is observed when the carbon dioxide concentration is increased and it is above normal. The increase in photosynthetic rate at pressures slightly exceeding the normal pressures is high but falls off as the concentration of carbon dioxide is increased. On the other hand, when the light intensity approaches that of sunlight, the photosynthetic velocities are greatly increased by an increase in the concentration of carbon dioxide.

In recent years attempts have been made to increase the yield of a crop by increasing the carbon dioxide concentration in the atmosphere surrounding the plants. Demoussy (1904) was the first to observe that plants grown in an atmosphere enriched in carbon dioxide showed an increase of 157·6% in excess of the control plants which were exposed to an atmosphere of normal carbon dioxide content, whilst the other plants had an atmosphere containing carbon dioxide to the extent of 0·15 to 0·18% for nearly two months. Kostyschew (1922) has reported that legumes are more affected by increase of CO₂ concentration than non-leguminous plants. Careful experiments carried on in Sweden by Lundegårdh (1924) in glass houses in which CO₂ was continuously passed, gave the following results for plants grown for 10 weeks.

	CO ₂ house.	Control house.	Excess.	
Cucumber—shoots	1·1807 kg.	0·890 kg.	0·917 kg.	103%
Tomatoes—shoots	2·700	1·310	1·390	124
Bean fruits	7·080	3·343	3·737	112
Mean CO ₂ content	0·0650%	0·043%	0·022%	51

Similar results were obtained by Fischer, Riedel, Jess, Owen and others. Although the results depend on the fertility of the soil and climatic conditions, they appear to be of great importance from the view point of practical agriculture. The artificial increase of carbon assimilation by an increase of CO₂ is possible by the nearness of big factories, which produce large amounts of CO₂ (the Krupp factories at Essen generate about 3000,000 kg. CO₂ per day). In this connection the following lines from Maximov's Plant Physiology (1930) will be of interest:

“The rapid development of the plants in hot beds underlaid with manure seems to be due not only to the high temperature thus produced, but also the abundant supply of carbon dioxide.”

Soil as a Source of Carbon Dioxide for Plants.

“Under natural conditions plants obtain CO_2 not only from the atmosphere, but also from the soil. Due to the processes of decomposition of the organic substances in the soil by different micro-organisms, CO_2 is liberated. Diffusing from the soil in the lower layers of the atmosphere, it is caught by the leaves of the plants. According to the calculations of Lundegårdh, a sandy soil, poor in humus, liberates about 2 kg. of CO_2 per hour per hectare, while loam and clay soils containing a greater amount of humus, eliminate about 4 kg. and forest soils, extremely rich in humus, produce from 10 to 5 kg. Moderately fertilized soils produce on an average 5 kg. of CO_2 per hectre per hour. A field of one hectare sown to oats consumes in the process of photosynthesis about 15 kg. of CO_2 per hour. Five of these are supplied by the soil; the other ten are obtained from the atmosphere. Lundegårdh observed that during the day the carbon dioxide content of the air is considerably lowered. At night the ‘respiration’ of the soil once more restores the balance. This balancing of carbon dioxide without profit or loss takes place only on soils of medium fertility. On poor ground, plants absorb more CO_2 than is lost by the soil, hence with the growth of the plants, the soil becomes enriched in humus. On the contrary, in soils very rich in humus the loss of CO_2 may exceed the accumulation of organic compounds by the plants. An especially great abundance of CO_2 has been found in forests under the cover of trees where in the lower layers of air, CO_2 may reach a concentration of 0.08%, instead of the average 0.03%. This high percentage of CO_2 compensates the shade plants to a certain degree for the lack of light.”

Influence of Intermittent Light.

Warburg (1919) working with *Chlorella* and intermittent light reported that in strong light the velocity of photosynthesis is greater than in continuous light of the same intensity acting for equal periods of illumination. The more quick the change of light and dark periods, the greater the velocity of photosynthesis. When the light is altered 8000 times per minute, the photosynthetic velocity is 100% higher than that in continuous light and photosynthesis is only 10% higher than in steady light when there are only four alterations per minute. When the light intensity is feeble, alterations of light and dark periods do not influence the velocity of photosynthesis.

Warburg explains this peculiar behaviour from the view point of the existence of a reaction taking place in the dark to a position of equilibrium but constituting one of the stages in carbon assimilation. The explanation of Warburg seems unsatisfactory. A better explanation is offered by the writer in the following pages.

Sir J. C. Bose (1924) carried on experiments on *Hydrilla* with intermittent light, the source being sunlight or point-o-lite lamp and observed with point-o-lite lamp, an enhancement of 21% in carbon assimilation with an intermission of 1 second; with intermission of 2 seconds, an increase of 8% was obtained. With sunlight also, a slight enhancement in photosynthesis was observed with an intermission for 0.5 seconds. When the periods of intermission are increased, the velocity of photosynthesis decreases to a minimum and then increases again.

In photochemical reactions, it has been frequently observed that a reaction started by light continues in the dark even if the light is cut off. This phenomenon of "after-effect" is of common occurrence in photochemical reactions and Dhar and collaborators (1926) have shown that this phenomenon is more pronounced when the light intensity is great and the reaction is highly sensitive to light. They have advanced the view that the life-period of the activated molecules produced by light absorption is considerably prolonged and that the slow reversion of the activated molecules into the inactive state is the main cause of the phenomenon of after-effect in photochemical reactions. Hence the enhancement of photosynthesis in intermittent light observed by Warburg and Bose appears to be a case of "after-effect" of the photochemical process involved in carbon assimilation. The photosynthesis started by strong light persists even in the dark and hence the amount of photosynthesis appears to be greater in intermittent light than in continuous light. It is interesting to note that plants grown in artificial light develop much better when irradiated continuously during day and night than when subjected to a period of darkness for 8-12 hours. It appears, that night's rest is not necessary for plants. The possibility of work without rest for several months seems wonderful.

Some Products of Photosynthesis.

It appears that the hexoses are the first products of photosynthesis. The assimilation of carbon dioxide takes place in definite parts of the cell in the green plastids. Non-green plastids, such as the

colourless leucoplasts and the yellow and orange chromoplasts (existing in fruits and petals of flower) cannot accomplish photosynthesis. The leucoplasts can convert sugar into starch as in potato tubers and other underground storage organs and this is in agreement with the view that the conversion of sugars into starch is a secondary reaction and not directly associated with photosynthesis.

There is difference of opinion regarding the first substance formed in photosynthesis. It is generally believed that the simpler hexoses, glucose and fructose are likely to be formed before the complex disaccharides are obtained in carbon assimilation, although several investigators, notably Brown and Morris (1893) concluded that sucrose must be the first sugar, which is formed in photosynthesis, because sucrose appears to be in excess of glucose and fructose in the plant leaf. The excess of sucrose was supposed to be converted into starch, whilst for translocation, sucrose was transformed into glucose and fructose.

It is well known that in the animal body the following equilibrium exists:

Parkin (1925) has pointed out that sucrose is a product special to the vegetable world, and he suggested that very likely the following equilibrium exists in the plant:

Chapman (1926), however, believes that the following direct and reverse changes occur:

Saposchnikoff (1890) reported that only 64-87% of carbon dioxide absorbed in the plant leaf appears in the form of carbohydrates. If this observation of Saposchnikoff be correct, it appears that other products are simultaneously formed along with carbohydrates in photosynthesis. If the carbohydrate formed in photosynthesis is a hexose then from 1 g. of carbon dioxide absorbed 0.68 g. of the carbohydrate will be formed. If starch is formed then 0.613 g. is

expected from 1 g. of carbon dioxide and in case of sucrose, 0.647 g. is to be formed.

Krascheninnikoff (1901) concluded that besides carbohydrates other substances are formed in photosynthesis.

Sir J. C. Bose (1924) from his experiments with *Hydrilla* obtained the value 0.8906 for the theoretical ratio,

$$\text{Glucose/Oxygen} = 180/192 = 0.9406.$$

It appears from these results that carbohydrates are not the only products of photosynthesis but along with them fats and proteins are likely to be synthesised. Meyer (1917) advanced the view that oil drops, which appear in the chloroplasts of *Vaucheria* are directly formed by photosynthesis.

Moreover, several authors have reported that small amounts of hydrogen peroxide can be detected in photosynthesis. It may be possible that the hydrogen peroxide detected in leaves is a product of respiration. Looking at the whole problem from a broad point of view, it appears that formaldehyde, which is the first product of photosynthesis, polymerises to hexoses, which in their turn, are converted into sucrose. This carbohydrate in presence of light becomes inverted into a mixture of fructose and glucose as has been observed by Dhar and co-workers (1921). Hence there appears to be an equilibrium between the amounts of sucrose and hexoses in plants. In the subsequent pages it will be shown that proteins are likely to be formed in nature by the interaction of formaldehyde and carbohydrates and nitrates or nitrites present in plants. Hence along with the carbohydrates, proteins are formed by photosynthesis in plants. But the chief product of photosynthesis is certainly carbohydrate, and the hexoses formed from the polymerisation of formaldehyde appear to be the first products in carbon assimilation.

Baeyer Theory of Formaldehyde Formation in Photosynthesis.

Most of the theories on the mechanism of photosynthesis in plants postulate the formation of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water in presence of light and the polymerisation of formaldehyde to reducing sugars. It is assumed that in the first stage, considerable amount of energy is absorbed but in the second stage, not much energy absorption is necessary.

The originator of the hypothesis regarding the formation of formaldehyde as the first stage in photosynthesis and its condensation to

reducing sugars was the great organic chemist Adolf Baeyer. His theory rests mainly on the observation of Butlerow (1861) that trioxymethylene, which is a condensation product of formaldehyde, forms a syrupy substance behaving like sugar when heated with an alkali. Baeyer's theory published in 1870, may be briefly summarised as follows:

Bayer assumed that under the influence of light, the carbon dioxide absorbed by chlorophyll, undergoes decomposition into oxygen and carbon monoxide, which is fixed up by the chlorophyll and oxygen escapes. The carbon monoxide is assumed to react with hydrogen and forms formaldehyde, which in its turn polymerises to glucose as was first observed by Butlerow in 1861. He observed the formation of sugars from formaldehyde in presence of alkali. Baeyer assumed the formation of sugar from formaldehyde under the influence of the cell contents and possibly of alkalis. Baeyer is silent regarding the origin of the hydrogen necessary for the formation of formaldehyde from carbon monoxide. Several authors after Baeyer have assumed that water is decomposed into hydrogen and oxygen, the hydrogen being taken up in the formation of formaldehyde and the oxygen is set free. It is well known that in ultraviolet light water is decomposed into hydrogen and oxygen but no evidence is available whether in the plant, this decomposition takes place in presence of those radiations which lead to photosynthesis in the green plant. Some authors, however, ascribed the production of hydrogen to causes other than the decomposition of water.

Baeyer's theory received considerable support in view of the observation, that the ratio of CO_2 absorbed and O_2 given out is unity and this relation is satisfied if we assume that formaldehyde is the first product formed in photosynthesis.

Detection of Formaldehyde in Plants.

Several authors notably Reinke (1881), Curtius (1897), Pollacci (1900-1907), Grafe (1906), Kimflin (1907), Gibson (1908), Chodat and Schweizer (1915) and others reported the formation of formaldehyde in green leaves after illumination. On the other hand, Maze (1920) Rouge (1921), and Sabalitschka and Riesenbergl (1924) could not detect any formaldehyde in plant tissues. Moreover, Spoehr (1913), and Fincke (1913), reported that in presence of light various organic substances present in the plant tissue decompose in light with the formation of formaldehyde. It appears from the foregoing observa-

tions that the formaldehyde in the assimilating plant tissues has not been proved beyond doubt. Recently Klein and Werner (1926) conclude from their experiments that formaldehyde and acetaldehyde occur in green leaves. Only formaldehyde was detected in leaves in which photosynthesis has occurred. It was not present in leaves kept in an atmosphere free from carbon dioxide or grown in darkness and in leaves poisoned by phenylurethane or hydrocyanic acid. On the other hand, acetaldehyde was detected in the leaves kept in the dark or those poisoned. Barton-Wright and Pratt (1930), however, have reported that formaldehyde is not a product of photosynthesis in plants but is generated by the action of light on bicarbonates and carbonic acid present in the outside water.

Experiments on Feeding with Formaldehyde.

If formaldehyde was an intermediate product of photosynthesis plants should be able to absorb this product from an atmosphere containing this substance and grow without the presence of carbonic acid. Numerous experiments have been carried on this line, and there is a general agreement amongst workers on this problem that formaldehyde in low concentrations can act as a plant food. Thus Loew (1899) and Bokorny (1888-1911) reported that in absence of carbon dioxide, but in presence of the formaldehyde-sodium bisulphite compound, *Spirogyra* can produce starch. Similarly Boitreux (1920), Moore and Webster (1920) and others reported the utilisation of formaldehyde by different plants. Grafe and Viser (1911), and Miss Baker (1913) could utilise gaseous formaldehyde as plant food in light, whilst the same result was obtained by Jacobi (1919-29) and Sabalitschka and Reisenberg (1924) in the dark, with several plants. Moreover, Bodnar, Roth and Bernauer (1927) observed an increase in the dry weight and the amount of carbohydrate in leaves exposed to formaldehyde vapour. According to Sir J. C. Bose (1924) formaldehyde, in small doses, serves as stimulant to the growth of plants.

Reduction of Carbonic Acid and Formation of Formaldehyde in vitro from Carbonic Acid and Bicarbonates.

From the chemical point of view, the main reaction involved in the first stage of photosynthesis seems to be the reduction of carbonic acid to formaldehyde.

Hence, to imitate the main chemical change involved in photosynthesis numerous chemists have attempted to reduce carbonic acid and bicarbonate solutions *in vitro* by different reducing agents. Thus Lieben (1895) and Ballo (1884) reduced carbonic acid to formic acid by the action of sodium and other amalgams, whilst Moissan (1902) obtained potassium formate by the reduction of carbonic acid by the action of potassium hydride. Fenton (1907) by the action of metallic magnesium on carbonic acid obtained formate as the chief product with traces of formaldehyde. On the other hand, Dhar and Atma Ram (1932) obtained considerable amounts of formaldehyde by the reduction of potassium bicarbonate solutions by powdered metallic magnesium without any trace of formate. This reaction also takes place with carbonic acid instead of bicarbonate. In place of metallic magnesium, cerium, tungsten and iron with carbonic acid have been used with similar results. This reduction of carbonic acid to formaldehyde is accelerated by sunlight. The importance of this research lies in the fact that carbonic acid and bicarbonates are directly converted into formaldehyde, which appears to be also the chief product in the first stage of carbon assimilation and that the reaction is accelerated by light.

Bredig and Carter (1914) obtained formic acid by the reduction of carbon dioxide by hydrogen under pressure in presence of palladium used as a catalyst and some carbonates. Schaper (1910) reduced carbon dioxide under pressure by ferrous oxalate.

By the action of silent electric discharge on mixtures of carbon dioxide and water, formic acid and formaldehyde were detected along with other products. Fischer and Priziza (1914) obtained formic acid and traces of methyl alcohol by the electrolytic reduction of carbon dioxide under 10-15 atmospheric pressures. Coehn and collaborators (1910) observed that dry carbon dioxide is decomposed by extreme ultraviolet light and Berthelot and Gaudechon (1910) reported that when hydrogen and carbon dioxide are exposed to light, formaldehyde and its condensation products are formed.

Reduction of carbonic acid in presence of different catalysts has also been effected in presence of light. Thus Usher and Priestley (1911) and Moore and Webster (1913) obtained traces of formaldehyde by exposing carbonic acid and water in presence of ferric and uranium salts, colloidal ferric hydroxide and some dyes, to ultraviolet and visible light. Stoklasa and Zdobnický (1911-1913) obtained formaldehyde when carbon dioxide and hydrogen with potassium hydroxide were exposed to ultraviolet light. Dhar and Sanyal (1925) obtained

formaldehyde by exposing carbon dioxide to tropical sunlight when it is passed in beakers containing conductivity water. The formation of formaldehyde is facilitated by the presence of methyl orange, methylene blue, ferric chloride, uranyl salt, chromium salt, colloidal ferric hydroxide, chlorophyll, etc. Gopala Rao and Dhar (1931), and Atma Ram and Dhar (1932) obtained formaldehyde by passing carbon dioxide into solutions and suspensions of different substances in water when exposed to tropical sunlight. Nickel carbonate, manganous chloride, and cobalt carbonate produce good results. Methylene blue and malachite green act as good photosensitisers in the formation of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water exposed to tropical sunlight. It is interesting to note that in presence of several fluorescent substances like rhodamine, fluorescein, cartharamine, safranin practically no formaldehyde was synthesised photochemically from carbon dioxide and water, although the fluorescent substances were decolourised in presence of sunlight. Moreover, formaldehyde has also been obtained by exposing solutions of alkali bicarbonates with different photosensitisers. With nascent carbon dioxide obtained by the interaction of hydrochloric acid and carbonate no coloured photosensitisers seem to be necessary for the formation of formaldehyde in tropical sunlight. In all these cases the yield of formaldehyde was much greater than the limit of sensitiveness of the tests employed. In view of this fact and the careful blank experiments always carried on side by side, there is hardly any doubt that formaldehyde is actually obtained from carbon dioxide and water in tropical sunlight. Moreover, by exposing solutions of potassium bicarbonate alone and with freshly prepared carbonates of zinc, magnesium and iron (ferrous) in sealed glass bulbs appreciable amounts of formaldehyde were obtained.

These researches of Dhar and collaborators have been confirmed by similar observations of Mezzadroli and his colleagues. Thus Mezzadroli and Gardano (1927) have obtained formaldehyde and small amounts of sugar, by exposing solutions of bicarbonates of different metals to ultraviolet light. Ammonium bicarbonate produces a better yield of formaldehyde than the alkali bicarbonates, but the greatest yield of formaldehyde is obtained from calcium bicarbonate. The amount of formaldehyde generated rises to a maximum and then gradually decreases owing to its oxidation and polymerisation. Moreover, Mezzadroli and Vareton (1928) have shown that exposure of these bicarbonate solutions and carbonic

acid to ultraviolet rays causes an increase in the reducing powers of the solution to a maximum followed by a rapid fall. The presence of colloidal or reducing catalysts increases the reducing powers. Mezzadroli and Vareton have also reported that the yield of formaldehyde and sugars is increased by the addition of metallic magnesium to the calcium bicarbonate solution. Mezzadroli and Babes (1929) have stated that the reducing power of a 5% solution of potassium bicarbonate exposed to ultraviolet light increases to a constant value in presence of an active variety of carbon. When zinc is present with the carbon the reducing power is still further increased.

Recent experiments carried on in these laboratories with great care along with blank experiments, show that formaldehyde is synthesised and detected when dilute solutions (5 %) of bicarbonates of the alkali metals are exposed to sunlight for about 4 hours in thin layers (0.5 cm. thick) either in open dishes (11 cm. diameter) or in dishes covered with silica plates at temperatures upto 30°, higher temperatures are prejudicial to formaldehyde production. The amount of formaldehyde photosynthesised per 100 c.c. of solution exposed is 0.00007–0.0001 g. Schryver's reagent is most sensitive for the detection of formaldehyde in small quantities. The amount of formaldehyde obtained from exposing the bicarbonate solutions in the same dishes placed in a bath at 40° is about one third of that obtained at 30° under identical conditions.

It will be of interest to note that in nature the amount of carbon assimilation is less at 40° than at 30° as will be evident from the following observations.

Miss G. L. C. Matthaei (1905) observed that the amounts of CO₂ assimilated by a cherry laurel leaf per 30 sq. cm. (about 8 sq. inches) per hour at various temperatures were:

Temp.	6°	8.8°	11.4°	15°	23.7°	30.5°	37.5°	40.5°	43°
Wt. of CO ₂ assimilated (g.)	.0002	.0038	.0048	.0102	.0070	.0157	.0238	.0149	.0102

But the total dry weight of organic matter produced during the whole life of the plant may not increase with temperature in this way. Bialoblocki's (1871) results with barley are as follows:

Temperature	...	0°	10°	20°	30°	40°
Dry matter formed (g.)	...	Nil	7.64	8.22	3.85	0.93

Similar results have also been obtained by Baly and collaborators *in vitro*.

In tropical countries, the optimum temperature of photosynthesis in plants, as a rule, seems to be higher than with plants growing in temperate climates.

Since 1870 when Baeyer gave out his formaldehyde hypothesis, numerous attempts have been made to obtain formaldehyde *in vitro* from carbon dioxide and water on exposure to light. Usher and Priestley (1911), Baly, Heilbron and Barker (1921), Dhar and co-workers (1925-32), Mezzadroli and collaborators (1927-29), Yoe and Wingard (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 886) and others obtained positive evidence of formaldehyde formation from carbonic acid or bicarbonates in presence of catalysts, when exposed to light. On the other hand, Spoehr (1923), Baur and Rebmann (1922), Porter and Ramsperger (1925), Bell (1931), Emerson (1929), Zschiele (1932), Mackinney (1932), and Qureshi and Mohammad (1932) obtained negative results, although Mackinney made the following significant statement

“ The status of this problem is extraordinarily involved, though it can hardly be doubted that some workers have succeeded in obtaining formaldehyde *in vitro*.”

Baly and co-workers (1927) seem to contradict their earlier results.

Formaldehyde in Rain Water and in Upper Atmosphere.

Recently a new aspect of the problem has been brought forward by the observations of Dhar and Atma Ram (1932), that freshly collected rain water always contains appreciable amounts of formaldehyde. It is believed that formaldehyde in rain water is formed by the combination of carbon dioxide and water vapour present in the atmosphere by the absorption of ultraviolet light from the sun.

We have continued our analysis of rain water for formaldehyde and we have observed that all samples of rain water contain formaldehyde varying from 0.00015 to 0.0012 g. per litre. It is interesting to note that the amount of formaldehyde per litre of rain water obtained after some sunny days is practically the same as photosynthesised by exposing solutions of potassium bicarbonate to sunlight. It may be that the amount of formaldehyde in both cases is controlled by the equilibrium,

We have shown that the incidence of lightning discharge and thunderstorm does not increase the amount of formaldehyde present

in rain water. On the other hand, we have observed that the amount of formaldehyde present in rain water is greater when the rainfall is preceded by some clear sunny days. Hence we are inclined to the view that formaldehyde in rain water is obtained as a result of its photoformation from carbon dioxide and water in the atmosphere.

It is well known that the following reaction requires ultraviolet of wavelength 2550\AA .

It is apparent that very seldom all the active rays are absorbed by a medium and hence it seems that all short ultraviolet rays coming from the sun will not be absorbed by the ozone layer present in the atmosphere. Some of the short wave radiations are likely to pass through the ozone layer and decompose water into H and OH, and these hydrogen atoms may reduce CO_2 to formaldehyde as has been observed by Bonhoeffer (1927) and P. Harteck (1933). This reduction of carbon dioxide by atomic hydrogen may be accelerated by the solar radiations. The heat of dissociation of water into H and OH is 110,000 calories. In other words, the energy required in the formation of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water is practically the same as that required in the breaking of H—OH link, which appears to be the first step in this process.

As the wave-length necessary for the formation of ozone (2020\AA) is shorter than those necessary for the formation of formaldehyde (2550\AA), it is expected that formaldehyde may be formed in the atmosphere at a height less than that of ozone.

Henri and Schou (1928) and Herzberg (1931) have shown that the ultraviolet absorption spectrum of formaldehyde vapour consists of 35 to 40 bands between 2500 to 3700\AA with a maximum at 2935\AA characteristic of aldehydes. The predissociation limit of formaldehyde appears to lie between 2680 to 2660\AA with diffuse bands. On irradiating formaldehyde vapour with rays of wave-length between 2800 and 2650\AA , Kirkbride and Norrish (1931) obtained a quantitative decomposition of formaldehyde into CO and H_2 .

It is apparent, therefore, that not only ozone but also formaldehyde present in the atmosphere absorbs short rays from the sun. Hence the absorption of solar radiations shorter than 2900\AA , which has been so far attributed to the presence of ozone, may be partially due to the formaldehyde present in the atmosphere.

Just as there is an equilibrium in the atmosphere between the oxygen and the ozone, it is evident, that the following equilibrium may exist in the atmosphere.

It is well known that the upper atmosphere is rich in hydrogen. Consequently due to the presence of hydrogen, the photo-decomposition of formaldehyde will be markedly hindered and appreciable amounts of formaldehyde may exist in the atmosphere.

From the foregoing lines it will be seen that the wave-lengths of radiations suitable for formaldehyde formation (2550Å) and decomposition (2660Å) are much nearer each other than in the formation (2020Å) and decomposition (2655Å) of ozone. Hence, there is greater likelihood of the decomposition of the formaldehyde as soon as it is synthesised than in the case of ozone, but due to the presence of hydrogen, appreciable amount of formaldehyde is likely to exist in the atmosphere.

Just as ozone can exist in the atmosphere at a height of a few kilometers above the earth's surface (compare Götz, Dobson and Meetham, *Nature*, 1933, 132, 281), formaldehyde can also exist at similar heights and that is why it can be washed down by rain water, which has been found to contain formaldehyde. We have made many careful experiments to see whether air on the surface of the earth contains appreciable amounts of formaldehyde. Large volumes of air were aspirated slowly through 20 c.c. of distilled water contained in a glass tube from 6-24 hours, but no trace of formaldehyde could be detected in the water by applying the Schryver's test, showing thereby that although formaldehyde exists in the upper atmosphere, it does not occur in the atmosphere near the surface of the earth.

Formation of Sugars from Formaldehyde.

Thanks to the researches of several chemists, the problem of the formation of reducing sugars by the condensation of formaldehyde is on a better footing than that of the photosynthesis of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water vapour. Butlerow (1861), Loew (1886-1889), Fischer (1892-1905), von Euler (1906), Nef (1914), Spöchr (1926) and others have shown that under various conditions, specially in presence of alkalis, formaldehyde is converted into reducing sugars in the absence of light.

Spoehr obtained traces of sugar by exposing 3% solutions of formaldehyde with zinc carbonate or potassium nitrate to sunlight. With lead and calcium hydroxides, which form sugars in the dark also from formaldehyde, the yield in light was greater. Inghilleri (1912) obtained sorbose by exposing formaldehyde and oxalic acid to light, whilst Pribram and Franke (1912) prepared glycollic aldehyde by exposing formaldehyde to ultraviolet light in quartz vessels.

Baly and collaborators (1924-1931) have carried on important researches on the conversion of formaldehyde to reducing sugars in presence of ultraviolet light. Baly (1924) reported that "with an initial concentration of 40% formaldehyde, the maximum reducing power is 8% calculated as glucose and with 20 litres of formaldehyde, this can often be reached after 14 days of continuous illumination." Recently Baly and collaborators (1927) have denied the formation of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water in ultraviolet light as reported in their previous work, but have obtained glycol, glycerol and reducing sugars from exposing formaldehyde to ultraviolet light. They have shown that when a 40% formalin solution containing an excess of calcium carbonate is placed in a tank kept at 30° and exposed to ultraviolet light from four quartz mercury vapour lamps for a month and the mixture is stirred, 80% calcium formate, 5.6% of calcium glycollate, and 15% of a mixture containing glycol, glycerol, pentaerythritol and some reducing sugars are obtained. According to these authors, the action of ultraviolet light is represented by the following scheme:

It is believed that the following stationary state is established by the action of ultraviolet light on carbonic acid:

When the concentration of carbohydrate is small and in presence of reducing agents, the reaction would proceed from left to right with the formation of carbohydrates, which would be photochemically decomposed to formaldehyde. Moreover, Baly, and co-workers (1931)

observed that when various sparingly soluble substances, capable of absorbing carbon dioxide are used and carbon dioxide was passed and the whole was exposed to ultraviolet light, complex organic compounds containing carbohydrates, which char readily and develop reducing power after hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid, are formed. Among the powders which behaved in this way were metallic aluminium, barium sulphate, freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide, basic carbonates of magnesium and zinc, ferric, chromic, and aluminium hydroxides with small amounts of thorium hydroxide deposited on kieselguhr, etc. They also used coloured substances like nickel or cobalt carbonates alone or deposited on kieselguhr with small amount of thorium carbonates in aqueous carbonic acid and visible light. The organic substances formed reduced Benedict's solution, gave the Rubner and Molisch reactions and formed a solid osazone. Under comparable conditions the use of visible light and coloured surfaces gave a greater yield of organic matter with a higher carbohydrate content than the use of ultraviolet light and white surfaces. It appears that the exclusion of ultraviolet light prevents the photo-decomposition of the carbohydrates formed. When a solution of ammonium carbonate containing a suspension of nickel or cobalt carbonate is exposed to visible light, complex nitrogenous organic compounds are formed.

Baly and collaborators have pointed out that the thermochemical equation,

requires the wave-length $2552\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ for the activation of carbonic acid by means of radiation alone. Since photosynthesis occurs in the plant with visible light, some other mode of activation must be discovered. These authors state "the total quantity of energy necessary for photosynthesis to take place is supplied in two separate amounts, one quantity being given when the adsorption on the surface takes place, and the second quantity being given out by light". It should be pointed out that a similar behaviour is observable with several other photochemical reactions, which are sensitised by different substances.

Recently Baly and Hood (1929) have shown that if the yield of carbohydrates (weight of photosynthesised organic matter soluble in absolute methyl alcohol) obtained from the presence of specially purified suspension of nickel carbonate (50 g.) in 1000 c. c. of water, is plotted against the temperature, the relation is found to be

a linear one between 5° and 31° (maximum yield being 0.0783 g.) after which there is a rapid decrease of yield. The values of the temperature coefficient for a 10° rise are in good agreement with those observed by Warburg (1919) with the unicellular alga, *Chlorella* under constant illumination. Baly and Hood have pointed out the close analogy between the photosynthesis *in vitro* and *in vivo* with special reference to the researches of Miss Matthaei (1905) on the assimilation of carbon dioxide at various temperatures and to the fact that the process both in the living leaf and in the laboratory has an upper and a lower temperature limit.

Dhar and co-workers (1925-1932) have studied the conversion of formaldehyde solutions to reducing sugars in presence of catalysts in sunlight. Dhar and Sanyal (1925) and Atma Ram and Dhar (1932) obtained reducing sugars by exposing solutions of formaldehyde with ferric chloride to sunlight. When solutions of formaldehyde are exposed to sunlight for periods varying from 60 to 125 hours with catalysts like ferric chloride, zinc oxide, nickel carbonate, chlorophyll, methylene blue and methyl orange, reducing sugars are detected. The best results obtained so far are those with ferric chloride. It will be of interest to note that formaldehyde solutions when mixed with fluorescent substances like safranine, cartharamine, rhodamine, etc., and exposed to sunlight, do not form reducing sugars, whilst with chlorophyll, reducing sugars are produced. The sugars obtained reduced Benedict's solutions and gave the Molisch and Rubner reactions. On exposing 1% solution of formaldehyde in presence of freshly prepared dilute ferric chloride in thin layers in open dishes, reducing sugars can be obtained even after an exposure of 4 hours.

Influence of Temperature on Sugar Formation from Formaldehyde.

As the yield of reducing sugars on exposing formaldehyde solutions to sunlight was best with ferric chloride, it was thought profitable to determine the temperature coefficient of this polymerisation for a 10° rise of temperature. 800 C. c. of 3% formaldehyde solutions were exposed in a sealed bulb with enough ferric chloride to sunlight for 45 hours at 30° and 40°. After the removal of the ferric and ferrous salts formed by the reduction of the ferric chloride, the solutions were evaporated to complete dryness, and freed from formaldehyde. The dried mass was extracted with pure methyl alcohol. The residue obtained after removal of methyl alcohol was estimated

by the reduction of Fehling's solution. The amount of CuO obtained at $30^{\circ} = 0.061 \text{ g.} \equiv 0.1355 \text{ g.}$ of glucose, whilst at 40° the $\text{CuO} = 0.077 \text{ g.} \equiv 0.16 \text{ g.}$ of glucose. Hence the temperature coefficient for a 10° degree rise of temperature between 30° and 40° for the conversion of formaldehyde solutions to reducing sugars in presence of ferric chloride in sunlight is 1.2. In this connection, it will be of interest to note that van Amstel (1916) obtained the value 1.26 for 10° rise of temperature between 24° and 36.5° in photosynthesis with *Elodea* and Sir J. C. Bose obtained the value 1.22 for a 10° rise between 20° and 30° in photosynthesis with *Hydrilla*.

Photosynthesis of Nitrogenous Compounds.

From our experiments on exposing solutions of formaldehyde and nitrite or ammonia to sunlight, we observe that methylamine is fairly easily obtained. Hence, it appears that in the absence of carbohydrates the products of photosynthesis of nitrogenous compounds will essentially consist of substances like pyridine, piperidine, etc., formed by the reaction of methylamine and formaldehyde and these compounds have actually been obtained by several workers including ourselves. In presence of carbohydrates, however, we are likely to obtain alkaloids like nicotine, but especially amino-acids by the reaction of aldehydes of the monobasic and dibasic acids obtained from starch and carbohydrates with ammonia or methylamine. It appears, therefore, that in nature, also amino-acids, the precursors of proteins are formed by the reactions of ammonia or methylamine on the derivatives of carbohydrates and that is why the formation of proteins in plant goes hand in hand with the formation of carbohydrates, which require light. Several workers have reported that the formation of proteins in nature is facilitated by the presence of carbohydrates or light. Moreover, it appears that protein formation in plants is likely to be facilitated by the presence of fats, which yield glycerol readily. It has been shown by Dhar and collaborators that reducing sugars are obtained by exposing glycerol to sunlight. Recently we have observed that reducing sugars are obtained by exposing to air and light solutions of tartaric acid and other organic acids in presence and absence of photocatalysts. Hence the presence of tartaric acid or other hydroxy organic acids may also favour the formation of proteins in plants.

It is well known that in the animal body, proteins are converted into glucose. In the plant kingdom the formation of proteins is

facilitated by the presence of glucose. It appears, therefore, that in photosynthesis protein formation is likely to take place when some carbohydrates have already been formed.

Appreciable amounts of nicotine have been photosynthesised and the molecular weight of the base determined from the chloroplatinate of the base on exposing dilute solutions of ammonia, formaldehyde and cupric salts in presence of catalytic surfaces like ZnO, TiO₂, etc., to sunlight for about 80 hours. Moreover, when solutions of glycol and potassium nitrate are exposed to sunlight for about 8 hours in presence of TiO₂ as a photocatalyst, tests for glycine are obtained. Similarly a solution containing glucose and potassium nitrate with TiO₂ as a photocatalyst when exposed to sunlight for the same period, appears to produce arginine. Longer exposure causes the disappearance of the amino-acids photosynthesised, probably due to their photo-oxidation. Solutions of ammonium lactate form amino-acids when exposed to light. These amino-acids obtained in photosynthesis can be readily tested by the valuable "ninhydrin" test.

The mechanism of photosynthesis of proteins by the injection of potassium nitrate in the stem of *Helianthus annuus* has been studied by Varadachar (1932).

Influence of Temperature on Photosynthesis.

Many plant physiologists following the lead of Blackman have applied the van't Hoff rule to plant temperature studies. The application of the Arrhenius relation has been found to be general with ordinary chemical reactions. When the same relation is applied to the results actually obtained regarding the influence of temperature on photosynthesis in plants, it fails, as will be evident from the following table obtained from Warburg's results (1919).

Light intensity.	Observed $\frac{k_t + 10}{k_t}$.	Calc. $\frac{k_t + 10}{k_t}$.
16	2.0	4.11 between 16° and 25° (taking 4.7 between 5° and 10°).
45	2.0	4.01 between 10° and 20° (taking 4.3 between 5° and 10°).
45	1.6	3.66 between 20° and 30° (taking 4.3 between 5.4° and 10°).

These results have been calculated by applying the Arrhenius relation. It appears that the temperature coefficients of photosynthesis do not obey the Arrhenius relation, which has been found to be universally applicable to ordinary chemical reactions investigated so far and no case of failure has been reported. In photosynthesis, the observed values are always smaller than the calculated values. The reasons of the non-applicability of this relation to photosynthesis in plants are: (i) the greater influence of temperature on the respiration process than that on photosynthesis and, (ii) the harmful influence of high temperature on the chloroplast.

When the temperature of a plant system undergoing photosynthesis is increased the velocity of photosynthesis is increased but to a smaller extent than that of respiration. Consequently, the temperature coefficient of the observed photosynthesis will appear to be smaller than when the reversible reaction was not present. Moreover, the chloroplast in the protoplasmic cell which is likely to be active in the photosynthetic process starts undergoing deterioration when the temperature is greater than 20° and may be partially destroyed when the temperature is still greater. This is evident on comparing the results obtained by Warburg and those calculated from the Arrhenius relation. The observed temperature coefficients between 16° and 25° and between 10° and 20° are nearly half of the calculated values, whilst the observed temperature coefficient between 20° and 30° is much less than half of the calculated value. The pernicious influence of high temperature on physiological and enzymatic and bacterial processes is well known. In most cases the optimum temperature in these reactions is round about 20° . Moreover in plant photosynthesis, there is an additional factor namely, the reverse reaction, *e.g.*, respiration, which is also simultaneously going on and is counterbalancing the photosynthetic reaction and hence, the influence of temperature on photosynthesis is less pronounced due to these counteracting agencies.

It has been observed that in the case of some chemical reactions, the temperature coefficient can have the high value 7.2. Hence it is no wonder that the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis at low temperatures (say between 5° and 10°) has the value 4.3. It seems probable that the photosynthetic reaction is not an adsorption process of which the average temperature coefficient is in the neighbourhood of 1.2 for a ten degree rise of temperature, but it is controlled by a truly photochemical change having a moderately high

temperature coefficient. In several communications from our laboratories it has been shown that the photochemical reactions need not have temperature coefficients approaching unity, but can have values as high as 4. From the foregoing considerations, it is clear that it is needless to assume that the photosynthetic process involves two reactions. It is believed that in high light intensity the chemical reaction ("Blackman reaction" as designated by Warburg) is determining the total velocity of the reaction, because for a ten degree rise of temperature between 15° and 25°, the velocity of the photosynthesis is doubled. On the other hand, in low light intensity, the temperature coefficient instead of being 2 as with intense light, is 1.06 and hence it has been assumed that the chemical reaction is not the controlling factor as in the previous case; but the photochemical reaction with a low temperature coefficient determines the photosynthetic rate at low intensities of light.

In presence of intense light, the photochemical reaction causing the photosynthesis and having a moderately large temperature coefficient is predominant and the counteracting influence of the respiration process, which is not as much accelerated by light as the photosynthetic reaction, is not prominent. On the other hand, in presence of feeble illumination, the velocity of the photosynthetic reaction is not high, because this reaction takes place only in light and is proportional to the light intensity. In this case, the counteracting influence of respiration, especially at increased temperatures, becomes prominent and hence the influence of temperature on the observed photosynthetic rate is feeble.

Warburg (1919) has observed that the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis with the unicellular alga *Chlorella* is much less when the light intensity is feeble than when it is strong. Thus $kt + 10/kt$ between 16° and 25° with light intensity sixteen = 2.0 and $kt + 10/kt$ between 15° and 25° with a relative intensity of one = 1.06.

These results which appear to have been confirmed by other workers can be explained in the following way.

It has already been stated that in a plant, the following opposing reactions are taking place.

and the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis is less than that of respiration. Hence, when the light intensity is feeble, the velocity of photosynthesis is small and is slightly greater than that of respira-

tion at the same temperature. Now when the temperature of the system is raised through ten degrees, the velocity of the photosynthesis will be increased to a smaller extent than that of respiration. Consequently the temperature coefficient of the observed photosynthesis may be unity or less.

Moreover, in nature when the temperature of the air is high, the plants gain no material through photosynthesis because of the high respiration, whilst at lower temperature with the same light intensity, food materials are formed in the plant.

Willstätter and Stoll (1918) have reported that leaves of low chlorophyll content exhibit a lower acceleration with increasing temperature than the leaves of high chlorophyll content. Thus leaves of *Ulmus* with low chlorophyll content showed a temperature coefficient of 1.34 and with high chlorophyll content of 1.53 between 15° and 25°. These results of Willstätter and Stoll can be explained from the view point already advanced.

The temperature coefficient (1.53) of the photosynthesis with chlorophyll-rich leaves is greater than that with chlorophyll-poor leaves (1.34), although the photosynthesis is not at all directly proportional to the amount of chlorophyll in the leaves. Willstätter and Stoll find that temperature variations do not affect the rate of photosynthesis of the yellow varieties as much as the normal ones. In the yellow varieties, the amount of photosynthesis being small, the compensating influence of respiration becomes prominent and hence temperature does not appear to influence photosynthesis with these varieties to the same extent as the normal ones with more chlorophyll.

Moreover, differences in light intensity have more profound effect on the yellow varieties than on the normal ones and the time factor appears more slowly than with the normal ones. It is well known that photosynthesis increases with the light intensity and the chlorophyll content of the leaves. Now in the case of leaves containing much chlorophyll, the velocity of photosynthesis will be high and may reach the maximum, even when the light intensity is not high and hence in these cases, the reaction will be less sensitive to the influence of light changes, because the reaction is already fast due to the presence of large amounts of chlorophyll. On the other hand, when the chlorophyll content is small, the reaction velocity is small and light will affect the velocity more markedly than in the previous case. This explanation is in agreement with the observations

of Willstätter and Stoll that in the chlorophyll-rich leaves, an increase of light intensity was without influence on photosynthesis; in fact the light intensity could be reduced by $\frac{3}{8}$ without affecting the rate of photosynthesis. Exactly similar exhaustion effect has been observed with several photochemical reactions where the velocity of the reaction may be proportional to $I^{\frac{1}{3}}$ or $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in some cases where the reaction is very fast.

Even at low temperatures, photosynthesis goes on. Thus at -6° , photosynthesis was reported in leaves of cherry laurels by Miss Matthaei. In Alpine shade plants, photosynthesis is observed at -16° and in lichens upto -20° . Jumelle (1891) reported the occurrence of photosynthesis at -25° , -35° , -37° and even at -40° . Whilst with plants growing in warm, temperate, subtropical climates and water plants, photosynthesis stops between 0° and 2° and in tropical plants, it stops between 4° and 8° .

On the other hand, many plants resist high temperatures fairly well. Thus McGee (1921) reports that joints of a prickly pear attains a temperature of 55° without any visible harm. Wurmser and Jacquot (1923) have observed that several marine algae, when warmed upto temperatures varying from 36° to 45° for a period varying from 1-15 minutes show a smaller velocity of photosynthesis when brought back to their normal temperature (16°). The decrease of photosynthetic rate depends upon the temperature and the period for which the plants were subjected to the high temperatures.

The Phenomenon of "Solarisation".

It is well known that not only high temperature but also long exposure to strong light affects photosynthetic activity. Thus Ursprung (1917) observed that a leaf of *Phaseolus* after 5 hours of illumination showed very deep coloration of the starch-iodine, while after 8.5 hours' illumination, the reaction was faint. This phenomenon can be observed with almost any source of light of sufficient intensity and the time required is proportional to the light intensity. The effect is first brought about in the red-orange portion, the region showing the best photosynthetic activity. With higher intensity, the shorter wave-lengths bring about in shorter time and it is apparently proportional to the photosynthetic activity of light. Ursprung has called this phenomenon "solarisation" as it is analogous to the

phenomenon of solarisation observed in photographic plates under similar circumstances.

It is expected that not only with starch but with other carbohydrates, similar effect will be observed. This behaviour has been ascribed to the inactivation of chloroplasts. After long exposure to intense light, the plant organs are assumed not to function, although they are not killed and on keeping in the dark for a period, again produce starch normally.

The inhibiting effect of long exposure to light of high intensity on photosynthesis has long been studied by Ewart (1897) and the inhibiting effect has been ascribed to the destruction of chlorophyll. Pantanelli (1903) explains the fatigue effects observed by him in bright light from the viewpoints of chlorophyll destruction and injury to the chloroplast plasma. The observations of Ewart on *Allium cepa*, which does not form starch, indicate that when leaves of this plant are exposed to bright light for 14 days or for a shorter period while being fed with sugar, the evolution of oxygen finally ceases. This inactivation apparently does not injure the cells or chloroplasts. After a few days in darkness, the capacity for photosynthesis is regained.

The foregoing facts are explained from the following considerations.

In plants the following equilibrium exists :

The direct action (photosynthesis) is being opposed by the reverse reaction (respiration), which will increase, according to the law of mass action with increase in the concentration of the carbohydrate, which is a product of photosynthesis. Consequently, with accumulation of carbohydrates or when the plants are fed with sugar, as was done by Ewart, photosynthesis is retarded and may stop altogether when the carbohydrate content becomes very high. When the illumination is high and it lasts for a long time, the carbohydrate content increases and along with it the respiration also increases, and thus the photosynthetic velocity falls off with time even when the illumination is continued. After a time, the respiration will more than counterbalance photosynthesis and the carbohydrates formed by the photosynthesis will be oxidised to carbon dioxide and water and will disappear on prolonged exposure. When the carbohydrates disappear the photosynthesis will again

begin. It has been known for a long time that the photosynthetic rate decreases with accumulation of the products of photosynthesis. Moreover, Saposchnikoff (1893) has demonstrated the inhibitory power of an accumulation of carbohydrates and that these cannot increase beyond a certain point. When the leaves of *Vitis vinifera* contain 23 to 29 % carbohydrates of dry weight, photosynthesis ceases and respiration predominates. Saposchnikoff has shown that as carbohydrates accumulate, decrease of photosynthetic rate takes place, whilst a decrease in the carbohydrate content results in an increased photosynthesis. These results are evident from the viewpoint of the reversible reactions already put forward.

Moreover, there are two other factors, which increase respiration, should be considered, *viz.*, (i) influence of light intensity on the respiratory process, and (ii) influence of increased temperature caused by prolonged light absorption.

Compensation Point.

The compensation point, *i.e.*, the light intensity at which the photosynthetic and respiratory activities of the plant compensate each other, decreases with decrease of temperature as will be evident from the following table.

Plant.	Intensity at 20°.	Intensity at 5°.
Spirogyra	174	26·7
Fontinalis	150	40
Cladophora	253·3	62·9
Cinclidotus	400	75

The foregoing results show that the light intensity which at 20° represented the compensation point produced an evolution of oxygen due to photosynthesis at 5°.

With *Cladophora*, with increasing temperature, the compensation point rises more rapidly than the rate of respiration determined in the dark; an increase of temperature from 5° to 25° causes the respiration to become 4·8 times greater in the dark, whilst the light intensity increases to 6·69 times.

The foregoing results as well as other facts regarding the compensation point can be explained from the following considerations:

1. Photosynthesis is proportional to the light intensity, there being no photosynthesis in the dark.

2. Respiration takes place in the dark but is appreciably accelerated by light.

3. An increase of temperature affects respiration more markedly than photosynthesis.

The fact that the compensation point rises with increase of temperature is due to the greater increase of respiratory activity than photosynthetic activity with increased temperature. The respiratory activity of the plant, which counterbalances the photosynthetic process, increases much more than photosynthesis at higher temperatures and consequently, the light intensity must be increased to cause more photosynthesis to counteract the increased respiratory activity. There is another reason for further increase in the respiratory activity of the plant. Hitherto, it has been assumed by most of the plant physiologists that the process of respiration is not accelerated by light. But it is evident from the researches of Dhar and collaborators (*vide*, "New Conception on Biochemistry") that animal metabolism is markedly accelerated by light absorption. Hence, it seems pretty certain that the respiratory process taking place in plants is also accelerated by light. Consequently the respiratory activity of the plant is accelerated by two agencies, *e.g.*, temperature and light intensity and thus the light intensity required for increased photosynthesis in order to counteract this high respiratory activity should be very high. Thus with increasing temperature, the compensation point should rise more rapidly than the rate of respiration because of its additional enhancement by light absorption and this is clearly borne out from the experiments on *Cladophora* in which an increase of temperature from 5° to 25° causes the respiration to become 4·8 times greater when determined in the dark, whilst the light intensity increasee 6·69 times, for the compensation point.

It is evident that under certain circumstances, when the temperature is high and the light is intense, the compensation point may not be attained even with intense light and the plant will evolve carbon dioxide like an animal even in presence of light. This is likely to happen frequently in tropical countries where at the sea level, the heat rays of the sun become very prominent and the temperature of the plant will be high and photosynthesis cannot counterbalance respiration under these circumstances. At higher altitudes, the light rays are more active than at the sea level and it is expected that at these altitudes, very seldom, respiration will exceed photosynthesis in sunlight.

These conclusions are corroborated from the experimental results of Hardar (1921) with sea plants in the polar zones where the light intensity is not very high. Thus Hardar records the following ratio of photosynthesis and respiration for different temperatures were obtained.

20°-22°	0·588	0·4427	0·4280
2°-3·5°	1·603	0·9207	2·059

The position of the compensation point of a plant with reference to temperature is naturally of great importance to the life of the plants and its relation to the environment.

Formaldehyde in Dew and its Formation from the Photo-oxidation of Organic Compounds.

Dew has been found to contain appreciable amounts of formaldehyde. The quantity of formaldehyde is generally greater in dew than in rain water. The origin of the formaldehyde in dew seems to be the photo-oxidation of organic matter present on the surface of the soil. When solutions of organic substances like acetic acid, citric acid, glycine, malic acid, lactic acid, glycogen, acetone, etc., are exposed to sunlight and air, formaldehyde is readily formed. Dyes like malachite green, methyl violet, methylene blue, etc., also form formaldehyde readily on photo-oxidation. Tartaric acid, butyric acid, propionic acid and some dyes form smaller quantities, whilst oxalic acid, formic acid, glucose, cane sugar, starch, histidine, etc., produce very small amounts of formaldehyde from photo-oxidation.

It seems likely that the energy generated in the photo-oxidation of these organic substances supplies a part of the energy for the photo-formation of formaldehyde. We are of the opinion that in nature, the photosynthesis that is taking place in the plants is aided by the energy obtained in plant respiration, which goes on as long as the plant lives. The ease with which formaldehyde or other energy-rich compounds are formed in plants is partly due to their getting a constant supply of energy from the oxidation of the food materials present in the plant. We have postulated that the most important chemical change in the formation of carbohydrates in plants and in the formation of formaldehyde in nature from carbon dioxide and water is the photolysis of water into H and OH. The amount of energy required to decompose a gram

molecule of water into H and OH is approximately the same as that necessary for the formation of a gram of mole of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water. These are highly endothermal changes requiring radiations of wave-length 2550 Å (1,12,000 calories). In nature, however, photosynthesis takes place in visible light especially the red. We are of opinion that the energy derived from respiration in the plants already supplies a part of the energy necessary for the photosynthesis and thus rendering the photo-decomposition of water possible by longer wave-lengths. Although the adsorption of carbon dioxide and water by the chlorophyll of the leaf may partially activate these substances just as the adsorption of hydrogen and oxygen on a platinum or palladium surface renders them active, it appears to us that this activation of carbon dioxide and water by their adsorption on the leaf surface is less important than their activation by the absorption of energy from respiration.

There is an intimate relation between respiration and photosynthesis in the plant kingdom, because photosynthesis cannot proceed without the energy available from respiration for the partial activation of carbon dioxide and water vapour. The need of the presence of oxygen in photosynthesis is also explained from the same point of view.

It is easier to obtain from formaldehyde or any other energy rich compound from carbonic acid or bicarbonate solutions on exposure to light when a suitable exothermal reaction is taking place in the system along with the photosynthetic reaction.

A Theory of Carbon Assimilation.

The following appears to be the important steps in carbon assimilation.

(1) Partial activation of carbon dioxide and water at the leaf surface due to their adsorption by chlorophyll and other plant pigments. It seems that chlorophyll and carotinoids present in the leaf act as photosensitisers and as reducing agents in the photo-reduction of carbonic acid. (2) Further activation of the adsorbed CO₂ and water by absorption of a part of the energy available from respiration and the oxidation of carotin and the formation of activated carbon dioxide and water as products of respiration. (3) Absorption of light by chlorophyll and other pigments and the

dissociation of activated water molecules in the leaf surface into H and OH and the reduction of activated carbon dioxide molecules to formaldehyde by the atomic hydrogen produced from the sensitised photolysis of water. The amount of energy required to decompose a gram mole of water into H and OH is the same as that necessary for the formation of a gram mole of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water. (4) The polymerisation of formaldehyde to reducing sugars. (5) The formation of hydrogen peroxide from OH and the rapid decomposition of H_2O_2 into water and oxygen on the leaf surface.

The polymerisation of formaldehyde *in vitro* to reducing sugars is an exceedingly slow process even in presence of light. We have shown that it is accelerated by ferric salts. Moreover, it is known that in presence of alkali, reducing sugars are formed from formaldehyde. Light accelerates this reaction. How the formaldehyde formed on the leaf surface undergoes rapid polymerisation is still unknown. This theory of carbon assimilation appears to have more experimental evidence in its favour than those of Willstätter, Warburg, Wurmser and others.

It is interesting to note that the botanists are also realising the importance of chemistry in plant metabolism, as is evident from the following statement of R. W. Thatcher, an American botanist of repute:—"Hence we may say that the methods by which the plant machine (protoplasm) accomplishes its results are essentially and definitely chemical in character and may be studied purely from the standpoint of chemical reactions".
